

DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL, SOCIO-CULTURAL CONDITIONS AND SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE MUSLIM EAST IN THE 9TH- 11TH CENTURIES DURING DIFFERENT DYNASTIES

Boymirzayev Qahramon Hasanboyevich

Independent researcher of Fergana State University

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Abstract: The article examines the historical, socio-cultural conditions and social environment in the Muslim East, and the scientific-methodological basis of studying the interpretation of justice in moral views. Also, the development of the historical, socio-cultural conditions and social environment in the Muslim East in the 9th-11th centuries during different dynasties was analyzed.

Key words: Muslim East, historical, socio-cultural conditions, social environment, moral views, philosophical, justice, scientific-methodological basis, activity, historical-philosophical analysis.

INTRODUCTION. A deep study of the conceptual foundations of the religious and philosophical views of Eastern scholars, a deep analysis of their philosophical essence helps to prevent various mistakes, contradictions and misunderstandings. Today, it is necessary to study the socio-political, philosophical and religious views of the scholars of the East, comparative analysis and, based on this, the commonality of science and faith, the importance of Islam for the life of man and society, respect for peaceful life, respect for representatives of other faiths, great importance is attached to the comprehensive study and promotion of the essence of original humanity, which encourages us to live with kindness. Because "it is necessary to note with a thousand regrets that some forces in the world are trying to connect the religion of Islam with the ideology of terrorism, increasing the sentiment against Islam. The fact that this factor calls the Islamic world to become more cohesive" also requires a deeper study of its essence and philosophical basis.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Historical, socio-cultural conditions and social environment in the Muslim East in the 9th-11th centuries, the scientific and methodological basis of studying the interpretation of justice in the moral views of Abu Abdullah Rudaki A. Ashraf (USA), K. Y. Bosworth (England), François de Blois (France), Rypka (Netherlands), Dabashi, Hamid (USA), E.G. Brown (England), R.M. Chopra (India), Southgate, Minoo S. (Iran), A. Boboxonov, A. Zunnunov, N. Komilov, U. Mahkamov . studied by researchers such as

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. During the Umayyad period, "foreign

sciences" were hardly supported, but everything changed when the Abbasids came to power. Al-Mansur, the second caliph of the Abbasid dynasty, was very interested in astronomy and encouraged the study of Greek works in this field. In 765, he paid special attention to Greek medicine due to his stomach ailment. Harun al-Rashid, the fifth Abbasid caliph, continued to support such research. This was very important for the development of the science of logic. Al-Ma'mun, the seventh caliph from this dynasty, supported the teachings of the Greeks with his own excellent initiative, and showed special encouragement to Greek philosophy in particular. He paid the famous translator Hunayn ibn Ishaq with gold for the weight of the books he translated. Bayt al-Hikma, founded by Ma'mun, was a unique research institute specializing in the translation of documents related to Greek science and philosophy. The first head of this institution was the Christian scholar Yahya ibn Masawai, whose specialty was the translation of works on medicine. Hunayn's son Ishaq ibn Hunayn continued his father's work.

During the first century of Abbasid rule, astronomy and especially medicine were Baghdad's first steps into the Islamic world, through which Greek science and philosophy began its triumphant march. In such conditions, the logic presented by the Eastern Christian scholars was placed in the central place among all other Arabic sciences. Greek logic entered the Arabic language with the translation of the first books included in Aristotle's Organon. At the end of the first period of Bayt al-hikma, six of the seven books on logic were available in Arabic. Aristotle's work "Rhetoric" ("Science of adulthood") was also translated into Arabic. Theodore translated the First Analytics into Arabic. His translation was checked by Hunayn ibn Ishaq, and in this case it was recognized by the general public. There is also a translation of Topika, whose translator is given as Timotheus. Abdal Masih ibn Abdullah ibn Naim translated "Sophistica" from ancient Greek into Arabic around 830.

The above-mentioned translators often translated word for word from the ancient Syriac language into Arabic, and Hunayn ibn Ishaq rightly criticized this method and replaced it with a different method that pays attention to the content. He radically changed the Arabic translation of Greek philosophical texts and introduced the following innovations:

☐ direct translation of Greek texts that are comprehensible into Arabic or, after comparing their translations into the ancient Syriac language, start a new Arabic translation based on them;

☐ comparing different manuscripts in order to have a reliable text;

to translate texts not literally, but according to the content of large expressions.

The development of Aristotle's logic in Arabic began due to the fact that the best Greek texts on logic reached the Arabs, and as a result, interest in Greek science and philosophy spread. Reviews and independent studies played an important role in this. Such works were initiated by Abu Ishaq al-Kindi. Neither Hunayn nor his son created independent works on logic. In this regard, the first follower of al-Kindi was Thabit ibn Qurra, who worked with him in Bayt al-Hikma. He wrote commentaries on all the works of logic available at that time in Arabic.

It is known that the Seljuk dynasty managed the secular affairs of a centralized state while maintaining the official rule of the Caliphate of Baghdad, who was ruling the defunct caliphate. Nizamul Mulk, patron of science, who served as a minister for a long time during the reign of the Seljuk Malikshah, also supported scientists such as Abu Hamid Ghazali and Mahmud al-Zamakhshari. He developed the work of the observatory in Baghdad and gathered famous astronomers. On the initiative of Nizamul Mulk, madrasas named "Nizomiya" were opened in cities such as Bukhara, Herat, Nishapur, Samarkand, and Baghdad. The remarkable aspect of the development of science in this period is that many scientists created innovations in their fields.

The period of almost a century and a half rule of the Arabs in the territories of Central Asia could not extinguish the spirited struggle and aspiration of the independent peoples of this region for the independence of their land and homeland. In fact, by the beginning of the 9th century, the crisis situation in the Arab Caliphate, the political tension, the conflicting processes taking place in Khurasan and Mowarounnahr, and most importantly, the uprising of Rafe ibn Lais (806-810) in this area, caused the people of this region to for getting rid of the Caliphate's dependence, created favorable opportunities for gaining the country's independence. In particular, after the death of the famous caliph Harun al-Rashid (786-809), an intense struggle began between his sons - Amin and Ma'mun - to occupy the caliphate throne. This political conflict, which lasted for several years, not only put the center of the caliphate in a difficult situation, but also had a significant impact on the development of events in the regions subject to it. Ma'mun raised a large army and appointed Tahir ibn Husayn from Khurasan as its leader. In a battle near Ray, Tahir ibn Husayn al-Amin defeated his army and began marching to Baghdad. Tahir won again in 813 and captured Baghdad. Mamun rises to the throne of the caliphate. However, he did not go to

Baghdad until 819, and ruled from Marv. By his order, Tahir bin Husayn became the head of the Iraqi military administration and the military garrison of Baghdad.

In 821, Ma'mun appointed Tahir ibn Husain as viceroy of Khurasan in return for his great services to the caliphate. In this way, the Tahiri state was created and lasted until 873. Tahir ibn Husain, after gaining the reins of government, decided to use it to increase the country's independence, development and power.

The Tahirites attach importance to the development of socio-economic and cultural life, property relations, regulation of agriculture, improvement of the use of water resources, construction of water facilities, as well as moderation of taxes from citizens. The capital will be moved from Marv to Nishapur. For example, in one of the decrees issued by Abdullah ibn Tahir, it was emphasized not to "offend the peasants", without which the treasury would not receive sufficient taxes. However, in spite of this, Tahiri rulers did not actually protect the interests of the peasants, but rather the interests of large landowners and merchants. Therefore, during the Tahiry period, the common people, especially the peasants, were forced to live in dire straits and pay exorbitant taxes. In only 844 years, the amount of tax collected from them was 48 mln. formed the dirham. This was unprecedented for the conditions of that time. That is why farmers' riots occurred in Seistan and other regions of the country and intensified. The riots in the agricultural oases and the Ghazi movement in the eastern regions of Khorasan were combined and reached a large scale. The brothers Yaqub and Amir ibn Lays, who became the leaders of these movements and were originally coppersmiths, captured Nishapur in 873 and succeeded in overthrowing the Tahiri dynasty. As a result of this, the Saffari dynasty (Miskars), founded by Yakub ibn Lays, came to power. However, no matter how simple the new ruler Yaqub ibn Lays lived in private life, he tried to increase the combat power of his army, provide salaries to the soldiers, pay heavy taxes, other payments and obligations of the working people. remained unchanged as before. In the end, this situation shook the socio-economic roots of the rule of the Saffari dynasty and condemned it to destruction.

In the 9th-12th centuries, the material culture in Movarounnahr was continuously developing in its own style and forms. Local masters, architects, painters, potters, jewelers, and coppersmiths from among the people created wonderful architectural monuments and art examples that made the country famous to the world. Behind the continuous encouragement of science and

culture by enlightened rulers belonging to the Somanids, Ghaznavids, Seljuks, and Khorezmshahs, the potential and creativity of many talented people grew and rose. Countless rare and valuable books and manuscripts were collected in the libraries that were built and operated on the initiative of the rulers of that time, which are enjoyed by the people of the present generation. The rich library near the Samanid palace, where even a great man like Ibn Sina was surprised to meet for the first time, was one of such places of knowledge.

The importance of Islamic culture in the growth of the spiritual culture of the peoples of Central Asia has increased. Islam, not only as a religion, but also as a new spiritual direction, had a significant impact on the entire cultural process, on the strengthening of socio-cultural and educational relations among all Muslim countries. In this period, superstition, any kind of knowledge, respect for science, and freedom of religious movements took precedence in spirituality. Religious and worldly sciences developed in an inextricable relationship with each other. The traditions and sources of knowledge of ancient Greece, India and other countries were widely used creatively.

CONCLUSION. In short, the cultural development in the Muslim East in the 9th-11th centuries had a special and unique impact on the development of world science and culture. This positive event in the Muslim EAST can be called "Eastern Renaissance", i.e. "Eastern Awakening" without hesitation.

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